

“Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship”: A perspective analysis on Information Technology and Digital India-In the backdrop of an initiative towards transformation and empowerment. (Under the scheme of Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav)

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Abstract: The aim of ‘Digital India’ with the motto of “Power to Empower,” initiated in 2015, kicked off well, despite questions about the competencies & capabilities of India becoming Atam Nirbhar Bharat (Self-Reliant India) by 2020.

Digitalization is the New Pandemic in India. The Digitalization drive has started transforming the sectors like Education, Transport, Marketing, Communication, Health, Governance, Human Resources, Finance, Banking, and many more to the list.

The central idea behind dynamically propelling ‘Digitalization’ is to explore all possible ways of innovation in effectively integrating the overall Supply Chain Delivery System. The “New Education Policy-2020” is a promising step for bringing changes in the Indian educational landscape toward future preparedness and readiness of the country to become a Global Leader in the ‘Digital Economy’ without sacrificing the principles of Atam Nirbhar Bharat.

In recent times out of all the transformations, the Entrepreneurial Sector stands remarkable in re-building India’s Economy after the Global Covid – 19 Pandemic (2020-2021) setback. There is no doubt about the “Digital India Movement” contribution to boosting employability and Entrepreneurship.

Today is the era of Digital Entrepreneurs. Digital India represents a \$1 Trillion opportunity to grow the economy with the ability to sustain 55-60 million jobs. This digital transformation campaign is making the country digitally empowered in the area of business, commerce & management, engineering & technology, online infrastructure, enhancing internet connectivity, and many more. Will the digital empowerment of citizens create a knowledge-based society and Digital Economy in India?

Keywords: Digital India, Transformation, Empowerment, Entrepreneurship, Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

India’s share of Global GDP will be 20% by 2050. India is considered one of the potential superpowers of the World. It is projected to become a \$ 5 trillion Economy by 2026-27 & \$ 10 trillion by 2033-34. A decade ago, India’s GDP was holding the 11th rank in the World. By 2025, India will be more populous than China. Its population will also be much younger. More than 10 million new workers will join the labor force, every year for the next two years.

Today is Digital Era. In the era of digital transformation, India has discovered “Digital India”. Though the pace was gradual it was regular and steady. No doubt India is becoming a Global Brand. Indian Government aims to enhance the Digital Economy's contribution to 20% of GDP in the coming years.

India's goal is to become a Digital Nation. Digital India has given birth to Digital Entrepreneurs'. Digitalization is creating skill-enabled livelihood in all walks of life. There is enormous potential that is to be capitalized. India's youth are bringing revolution by spearheading towards conceptualizing the Digital Economy.

Today India's Economy is the 5th largest in the World with a GDP of USD 3.5 trillion. India is poised to be a trillion-dollar Digital Economy and could support 55 to 60 million digitally enabled jobs by 2025-26. It is projected that India going to be the World's third-largest by 2030 and second-largest by 2050.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

India is emerging as the fastest-growing Economy Globally. Indian Entrepreneurs are going Digital. The COVID-19 Pandemic (Global Crisis) has catalyzed the process of digital transformation throughout the World. A key challenge for India is how to govern and harness the surge in digital data for the global good. It had been experienced that global Internet traffic in 2022 exceeded all the Internet traffic up to 2016. Data Management has become a key strategic asset for the creation of both private and social value.

How these data are handled will greatly affect India's ability to achieve Sustainable Development Goals. For India, determining the best way forward will be difficult but becomes necessary. Data are multidimensional, and their use has implications for businesses, trade and economic development and human rights, peace, and security. Responses are also needed to mitigate the risk of abuse and misuse of data by States, non-State actors, or the private sector.

The revenue share of e Commerce-Electronics & Media amounted to 20.8% in 2021. The internet penetration in India is forecast to amount to 76.5% in 2026. The mobile phone subscriptions per 100 inhabitants in India are forecast to amount to 89 in 2026. The emerging technologies are creating opportunities for many Indian entrepreneurs, Start-ups, and firms in IT/ICT/ITeS/IT-enabled ShowBiz/IoT/Robotics operations.

In 2009, National e-Governance Division was created by the Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology (MeitY), Government of India, as an Independent Business Division under the Digital India Corporation. NeGD has been playing a pivotal role in Programme Management and implementation of e-Governance Projects and initiatives undertaken by Ministries/Departments, both at the Central and State levels.

India will proudly hold the Presidency of the G20 group of Countries from 1st December 2022 to 30th November 2023. G20 is the premier forum for International Economic Cooperation that plays an important role in socio-economic governance and global issues ranging from climate and environment, trade and investment, health, agriculture, digital economy, energy, anti-corruption, employment, education, tourism, and culture.

During India's Presidency, 4 meetings and side events for the Digital Economy Working Group will take place over the year (2023). In order to showcase India's advancement in Digital Technologies, it is proposed to create an extraordinary Digital Experience using emerging technologies.

Rani Suman (2016) concluded that the digital India project provides a huge opportunity to use the latest technology to redefine India the paradigms of the service industry. It is also critical that many projects may need some refinements to achieve the preferred service level objectives, transformation process, and re-engineering. **Midha Rahul (2016)** said that digital India is a great plan to develop India for information prospects but its unacceptable accomplishment due to inaccessibility and firmness to requisite can lead to its let-down. Indian citizens should work jointly to shape the knowledge economy. **Gupta and Arora (2015)** studied the impact of a digital India project on India's rural sector. The study found that many schemes have been launched in digital India to boost the agriculture sector and entrepreneurship development in rural areas. The Digital India program has also set the stage for the empowerment of rural Indian women. **Mistry (2005)** developed a theoretical frame to represent how the digital divide is formed and how it can be bridged by a good framework in underdeveloped nations. With respect to economic development, the Government can also play a more direct role with the help of the digital divide.

Against the above background, it becomes necessary to examine the perspectives of the Indian Government and its implications being a developing country. Today it is more important than ever to embark on a new path for digital and data governance in India. Digital technologies are not free from privacy breaches, cyber-attacks, and other risks.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this Research through this Case Study is to investigate and understand the essentials of a healthy ecosystem for the Digital Economy in India towards implementing transformative measures through information technology for empowering the Citizens. Moreover, the purpose of the study is also to explore the approaches and methods of our emerging Information Technology System & innovations in attaining a Sustainable Economy in India. The objective is to understand the perspectives on the “Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship” in India.

Future readiness & preparedness is full of challenges & opportunities. It is a serious concern considering the multidisciplinary business abilities across the fields of management, economics, engineering, information technology, finance, sciences, social sciences, and humanities.

One of the important outcomes of this Research-Survey will be to understand the gaps between Government Services (IT-enabled services designed models through various Government Schemes) and Citizen satisfaction. An effort has been also made to bring out the bottlenecks in the responsibilities & accountability of each stakeholder in the entire supply chain. The Study attempts to examine, “Will the digital empowerment of citizens create a knowledge-based society and Digital Economy in India?”.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A thorough study of existing literature related to the “**Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship**” in India, as well as the World, has been examined and probed for the essential attributes (problem statements) impacting and influencing the emerging trends in Information Technology and Digital India.

The probable major attributes which perhaps are primarily essential to be addressed are (5E’s) Environment, Evolution, Engineering, Entrepreneurs, and Economy for understanding and carrying out the perspective analysis on the initiatives undertaken towards transformation and empowerment through Digital India.

The Research design formulated here was to collect primary data on these five (05) variables through a structured questionnaire (hard copy & electronic) based on random sampling from the targeted population of Indian Citizens (Children, Adults, Middle Aged, Old, Senior Citizens) from different socio-economic segments of the society & community.

Understanding the limitations of the study the Researcher with great difficulty taking help of the Google form managed, twenty-eight (28) Economic Centres, one in each state was established at the Capital of the State, (i.e., a mix of families with their monthly earnings below the poverty line, middle class, moderate, affluent, wealthy formed the sample population) across India, was specifically focused, examined and considered for fifteen (15) respondents from each Economic Centre.

In total, the field responses of four hundred twenty (420 @15 each from scattered (28) Economic Centres representing each Indian State) respondents were recorded, examined, evaluated, and analyzed co-relating with the secondary data sourced from the literature review for understanding the emerging trends in “Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship”, with respect to Gap Analysis on Information Technology and Digital India. Based on these findings through Quantitative Analysis using simple descriptive statistical tools of percentage the Researcher has recommended and suggested valuable remedial measures in further transforming and empowering India.

V. PROBLEM STATEMENTS

What do you mean by “**Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship**”? The landscape of the Indian Economic System is under reformation with the implementation of Government schemes “Digital India Movement” & “Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav”.

Will the initiative of Digital India by the Indian Government create a holistic Economic System? To evaluate India’s presently emerging Economic System; challenges of the global processes, innovating & learning experiences, effectiveness, objectives, outcomes, and impacts following below attributes (5E’s) as variables have been designed for study as Problem Statements in the present Research in the backdrop of the major initiatives undertaken under the scheme of Azadi Ka Amrit Mahotsav initiated by Government of India.

5E's driving Digital India

Based on the literature review, the researcher observed, identified, realized, and analyzed that the Digital India drive is being impacted & influenced by the (5E's) which are Environment, Evolution, Engineering, Entrepreneurs, and Economy; the essentials in building and driving Digital India.

These 5E's have been focused on in the present study to carry out the perspective analysis on Information Technology & Digital India to understand the philosophy of "Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship".

1. ENVIRONMENT: Preparing India for a Knowledge Future

"The Economic Environment is Evolving Globally". The issues of Climate Change & Go-Green are impacting every country. The shift is towards Digital Industry (Manufacturing & Services). The demand for Information Technology (IT) enabled skilled manpower is increasing day by day. Opportunities for livelihood are being created throughout the country and the globe. Will the objective of the 'Digital India Movement' be achieved by 2035? Is our socio-economic & political environment conducive to supporting & sustaining the emerging digital environment globally?

The Digital Economy is the new emerging face competing with the Industrial Economy. Digital Models like "Public Private Partnerships" are being promoted & preferred and more exposed wherever feasible in areas like the adoption of Unique ID, restructuring of NIC, e-Governance, etc, towards citizen-centric service orientation. Digital India is being implemented with well-defined roles and responsibilities for each agency involved.

2. EVOLUTION: Utility to Every Citizen -Indian Government Mandates

India is caring for its Citizens. Can-With the evolving environment 'Utility Access' be provided to every Citizen by 2025 in India? The Government is becoming e-Service oriented. The evolution is seen in e-Businesses, e-Commerce, e-Education, e-Health Services, and almost all walks of life.

There are many Gram Panchayats and remote locations in the country where due to poor infrastructure 'High-Speed Internet' as a core utility still has not been made available to the citizens. The work on the mandate 'Cradle to Grave' digital identity - unique, lifelong, online, and authenticable is progressing at a snail's speed. The usage of Mobile phones and Bank account participation in digital and financial space at the individual level is rapidly increasing.

The Information Technology Ministry and Department are striving hard to make easy access to a 'Common Service Centre' within their locality. A lot of work on the concept of shareable private space on a 'Public Cloud' is being undertaken. With the rising scams and Cyber-crimes, the area of safe and secure Cyberspace in the country is being given priority for data secrecy.

3. ENGINEERING: Computerization-Capabilities & Competition

Digitalization is based on Engineering & Technology. Talent & Technology are going hand in hand in making tomorrow's Digital India. The imagining through innovative technologies is being gradually seen in reality as mandated in the reformative initiatives of the Indian Government for making it Digital India.

There should be no home or office without a computer is the motto of Digital India. The scope enhancement, Process Re-engineering, use of integrated & interoperable systems, and deployment of emerging technologies like Cloud & mobile are being undertaken on priority to further enhance the delivery of Government services to citizens. The Indian Government is promoting many medium and small Enterprises in 'Digital Businesses' through the schemes of MSME. (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises)

The role of Educational Institutions can never be forgotten in the uplifting of the fundamentals of computerization in the country in the 21st Century. In this, the Teachers, Engineers, Scientists, Researchers, Consultants, and many more have pooled their knowledge and innovation in synergizing talent & technology in engineering digital changes across the country.

4. ENTREPRENEURS: Global Role of emerging Digital Entrepreneurs

Will all Digital Entrepreneurs contribute to building a robust Digital Economy by 2025? Is India prepared to play the Global Role in meeting the challenges of the 21st Century?

More companies have started doing Digital Businesses. Goods & services are being digitized. The shift is from traditional ventures to digital ventures (involving digital goods & services). Now no Organization is free of digital activity. Due to the rapid rise of digital activities 'Digital Entrepreneurship' is evolving rapidly in India. There is a greater need for market orientation, handling cultural diversity, and computer-mediated communication.

5. ECONOMY: DIGITAL ECONOMY

"Economy by Entrepreneurship" is the new Global Mantra. The Employment is through Entrepreneurship. Indian Citizens are being encouraged and empowered to take up entrepreneurship. The government is becoming a facilitator more than a regulator. Do we have a Holistic Economic Model evolving? Can the implementation of the 'Digital India' program seek to transform India into a knowledge-based society and economy?

Is India's Economic System getting transformed and empowered? Can Information Technology up-gradation overcome unemployment disruption in India? Digital Economy is permanently penetrating and getting embedded into the National & Global Economy.

VI. ANALYSIS, FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

The (field & virtual) survey was carried out with the help of both (hard copy & electronic) questionnaires respectively and the selective respondents on sampling were interviewed (both in the field & through google meet mode/telephonically) for their views on the area of Research related to "Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship".

Based on their opinions and feedback the data was analyzed and accordingly outcomes have been worked out. The findings were then mapped with the secondary data available from the relevant review of literature in the area of study.

And it was interpreted to understand the perspectives of Indian Citizens scattered throughout the Country from different sections of socio-economic society on the "Digital Economy by Entrepreneurship" along with the gaps in the emerging trends in Information Technology and Digital India initiatives mandated by the Government of India after analyzing both the primary and secondary data.

Demographic Information Gathered

The Survey revealed that the gender response; the male is to female ratio was 55% to 45%. In the Age Group category of Citizens, it was observed as 27.5% were under 10-15 years, 36.5% for 15-25 years, 18.0% for 25-35 years, 9.0% for 35-50 years, 5.0% for 50-60 years, and 4% for above 60 years.

The respondents were categorized based on household earnings having minimum earnings per month were distributed as 28.2% for < Rs 5,000, 9.1% for >Rs 5000 & < Rs10,000, 9.1% for > Rs 10,000 & <Rs 15,000, 27.2% for > Rs15,000 & <Rs 25,000, 13.2% for > Rs25,000 & < Rs 50,000, 8.2% for > Rs 50,000 & <Rs100,000, and 5% for > Rs100,000.

Regarding the sources of earnings of the family, the respondents were distributed as 7% from micro-enterprises, 14% from small enterprises, 9% from medium enterprises, 5% from commercial businesses, 11% from purely digital enterprises, 24% from non-industrial businesses and the rest 30% of the sample represented the non-business community.

For the Relationship Status of the Individual respondents following can be summarized; 20% were children, 25% were adults, 18.2% were unmarried, 40 % were married and 11.8% were found to be divorced/separated. The type of family of the respondents was 27.3% for Joint and 72.7% for Nuclear. The distribution in the Income Category who participated in the Research Survey was 19.1% for those below the poverty line, 9.1% for the moderate middle class, 45.4% for the middle class, 16.4% for the rich middle class, 5% for the affluent class, and 5% for the wealthy class.

Interpretation

1. Did 'Digital India' with the motto of "Power to Empower," initiated in 2015, brought in transformation and empowerment in the true sense? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
2. Is Digital India's transformation enhancing the Knowledge Economy? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
3. Did, the "Digital India Movement" boost employability and Entrepreneurship? 32.3 % of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 4.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
4. Did you benefit from the national scheme "Digital India Movement"? 32.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 17.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
5. Comment on, "The forecast of 55 to 60 million digitally enabled jobs by 2025-26". 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
6. Do you think the unemployment rate has decreased in the people living below the poverty line due to the 'Digital India' drive? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
7. Perception: "Women Entrepreneurs are taking lead in Digital Start-ups". 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
8. Comment on, "Digitalization in Education has taken off well in India". 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
9. Thought on, "Digital Education is the tool for transformation and empowerment". 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
10. Do you appreciate the efforts of the Indian Government in the Education Sector? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
11. Opinion on, "India is experiencing appreciable changes in e-Governance". 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
12. Your thought on, "The dimensions of Marketing have been redefined due to the digitalization drive". 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.

13. Did India accomplish the vision of “Atma Nirbhar Bharat” by 2020? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement. The Researcher identified that majority of the respondents 54.6% disagree that the vision is achieved which is in line with the review of the literature and the latest updates.
14. Is India prepared to handle the country's phenomenally increasing internet penetration rate? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
15. Comment on, “Communication with digitalization has broken the barriers of distance and remote businesses are getting connected to the Global Market”. 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
16. Viewpoint on, “Customer is King as ‘Market is in Pocket’”. 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
17. Don't you agree that ‘e-Commerce’, has created enormous opportunities by establishing the Virtual Market linking all corners of the World with the application of Internet Networking? 18.2% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
18. Did not the concept of ‘Work from Home’, emerged as the new digital platform, redefining the opportunities for employment in the Digital Era? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
19. Has the Indian Government succeeded in reforming by improving the speed & quality of services through the implementation of internet-enabled “e-Governance”? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
20. Did the Covid-19 Pandemic (Global Crisis) act as a catalyst in bringing digitalization transformation in the health sector in India? 37.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 8.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
21. Will India emerge as a successful leader in holding the Presidency of the G20 group of Countries from 1st December 2022 to 30th November 2023? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
22. Are you aware of the methods for measuring the Digital Economy? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 18.2% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 9% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
23. Is the present percentage contribution of the Digital Economy to GDP satisfactory? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
24. Comment on, “Computerization, AI and emerging technologies have the potential to not just propel the economy but also create more jobs”. 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
25. Will the digital empowerment of citizens create a knowledge-based Society and Digital Economy in India? 27.3% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 9.1% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
26. Has “e-Kranti (Electronic Delivery of Services)” brought satisfaction to the Citizens of India? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement. The majority of the respondents 54.6% are not satisfied with “e-Kranti” Services.
27. Are you satisfied with the progress of ‘Digital Identity’ (Cradle to Grave)? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.

28. Comment on, "Indian Economy has moved to digitalization and usage of Information Technology". 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
29. Do we have a safe and secure Cyber-space in the country? 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.
30. Perspective on, "The Economic Environment is Evolving Globally". 9.1% of the respondents each Strongly Agree and Agree, 27.3% each Disagree and Strongly Disagree, and the remaining 27.2% had no opinion on the above problem statement.

Suggestion -Way Forward

The interpretation revealed mixed opinions of the total respondents surveyed in the study. The Researcher suggested that unless the Indian Economic System thinks qualitatively with the multidisciplinary perception for Sustainable Economic Growth & Development future readiness will be incomplete with respect to Global Economic Standards.

The Researcher brought to the surface that States should be given more flexibility to identify for inclusion of additional state-specific projects, which are relevant to their socio-economic needs based on the "Nine Pillars" as envisaged Broadband Highways, Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity, Public Internet Access Programme, e-Governance (Reforming Government through Technology), e-Kranti (Electronic Delivery of Services), Information for all, Electronics Manufacturing, IT for Jobs and Early Harvest Programmes.

VII. CONCLUSION

India is going "On-Line". Right from birth registration to death certificate, whether it is products, goods, services, health, banking, education, hospitality, travel, entertainment, or many more all should be available "On-Line" to Citizens of India.

Digital literacy is the first step in empowering citizens. The Digital India program is to prepare India for a 'Digital Economy' through "Digital Entrepreneurship". Digital India is an Umbrella Programme - covering many departments that are weaving together to make the Mission transformative in totality. The Digital India Programme will pull together many existing schemes which would be restructured and re-focused and implemented in a synchronized manner.

The "Make in India" drive made 'Digitalization' play a vital role in the flourishing of the "Digital Economy" by creating job opportunities in the country for youth. The ultimate aim of "The Digital India Movement" is to prepare Citizens for a Sustainable Knowledge Society. The existing and ongoing IT revolution, e-Governance, and e-Service initiatives are to be further revamped to align them with the principles of Digital India.

To summarize, "Citizen as Customer", India in the 21st Century is going to experience a commendable "Digital Revolution" to stand on its ideals of Self-Reliant (Atam Nirbhar Bharat).

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